

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NGWA LUM EPSE YENWONG****FIRST NAME: SYLVIA LYDIA****PROGRAM CODE: DDS D****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The did *not* use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401

1. How should evidence be used in an essay paragraph?

- To support the main point and followed by analysis.¹**
- Without analysis.
- Only in the introduction.
- In the conclusion only.

2. How should opposing views be treated in an essay?

- Ignored completely.
- Evaluated and examined.²**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 11.

² *Ibid.*, 9.

- Mentioned briefly without support.
 - Criticized harshly without reason.
3. What is the primary role of the European Investment Bank (EIB)?
- Managing the volume of money in circulation.
 - Conducting foreign-exchange operations.
 - Promoting the smooth operation of payment systems.
 - Providing financial support for investment projects.**³
4. What is the correct way to reference multiple EU regulations together according to the Style Guide?
- EU Regulations 2015/20 and 2015/21.
 - Regulations Nos. 2015/20 and 2015/21
 - Regulations (EU) 2015/20 and 2015/21.**⁴
 - Regulations 2015/20 and 2015/21.
5. How should you handle the citation of a newspaper article that appears in multiple editions with varying content?
- Indicate the edition consulted by adding an identifier like "final edition" or "Midwest edition" in the reference list entry.**⁵

³ Kate L. Turabian et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 92.

⁴ Ibid., 82.

⁵ Ibid., 269.

- Cite the article as you would for a magazine, without specifying the edition.
 - Only include the newspaper name in place of the author for an unsigned article.
 - List all editions consulted and their contents in the reference list entry.
6. How should you cite a thesis or dissertation that was accessed online from an institutional repository?
- Cite it as a book with the title in italics, without mentioning the repository.
 - Only include the author and year of publication in the citation.
 - List the document under the institution's name with the type of paper and a note about the online access.
 - Include the author, year, title, institution, and a URL if available.⁶**
7. What is the primary purpose of the population section in quantitative research?
- To describe the qualitative analysis methods used.
 - To summarize the literature review.
 - To clarify the characteristics of the group of individuals to which the findings are to be generalized.⁷**
 - To provide a detailed account of the dissertation findings.
8. What is the main reason for describing the setting in a dissertation title?

⁶ Ibid., 275.

⁷ James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, 2nd ed. (Tallahassee: Florida State University, 2017), 46.

- To ensure the reader knows where the author conducted their undergraduate studies.
 - To acknowledge the role of the setting in the research and its importance for generalizability.⁸**
 - To make the title longer and more descriptive.
 - To comply with university formatting guidelines.
9. Which document does the guide reference for advice on improving writing style in plain English?
- Evaluated The Plain English Guide by Martin Cutts examined.⁹**
 - Ignored completely.
 - Mentioned briefly without support.
 - Criticized harshly without reason.
10. What is the primary goal of the European Commission's English Style Guide when addressing legal or bureaucratic language?
- To simplify the language at all cost.
 - To eliminate all specialist terms.
 - To use as many technical terms as possible.
 - To embed specialist terms in straightforward English syntax.¹⁰**

⁸ Ibid., 24.

⁹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators*, 8th ed. (European Commission, 2021), 4.

¹⁰ Ibid., 65.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

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Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Booth, Wayne C., Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, Joseph Bizup, William T. Fitzgerald, and The University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. Ninth edition. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.